

THE IMPACT OF SMART WAREHOUSE APPLICATIONS ON SUSTAINABILITY: A QUALITATIVE STUDY*

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Abstract

As a result of the increasing impact of concepts such as sustainability, digitalization, and globalization on businesses, logistics and warehouse management practices are undergoing significant transformation. In this context, smart warehouse systems provide substantial support to businesses in terms of operational efficiency, cost advantage, speed, accuracy, and environmental sustainability. The aim of this study is to examine the effects of smart warehouse technologies on sustainability performance and on the dimensions of sustainability, namely environmental, economic, and social sustainability. The study was conducted at the Çumra Sugar Factory in Konya, which utilizes a smart warehouse system and granted permission for the research, between June 2025 and June 2026. The participants of this qualitative study consisted of smart warehouse managers at the Çumra Sugar Factory. The data were collected using a semi-structured interview technique and analyzed through content analysis using MAXQDA version 10. As a result of coding and analysis of the data, two main themes and nine sub-themes were identified. According to the research findings, it was observed that smart warehouse systems lead to a significant increase in efficiency. It was determined that real-time data management, automation technologies, barcode systems, and Warehouse Management System (WMS) software used in storage processes enhance the effectiveness of inventory control processes, accelerate shipment operations, and make significant contributions to reducing human-induced error rates. In conclusion, it has been determined that smart warehouse systems are not only a technological transformation but also provide a strategic structure that ensures sustainability, organizational efficiency, and competitive advantage. Therefore, it is considered that businesses should manage their digital transformation processes in an integrated manner with sustainability policies.

Keywords: Smart warehouse systems, Sustainability, Industry 4.0, Logistics management, Digital transformation, Sustainable warehouse management, Qualitative study

* This study was derived from a master's thesis.

1. Introduction

In the twenty-first century, the concepts of globalization, digitalization, and sustainability have become frequently studied and highly prioritized topics in business literature and among professionals. Similarly, one of the other prominent topics has been supply chain management. Supply chain management stands out as a strategic area in creating competitive advantage (Akbal, 2022). Among the important application areas of supply chain management, warehouse

management is located at the center of logistics processes and plays a critical role in terms of both cost and environmental performance.

Traditional warehouse systems have operated for many years based on manual processes. However, the increasing product variety, speed expectations, the growth in e-commerce volume, and the pressure of customer satisfaction have led these systems to become insufficient. This situation has directed businesses toward faster, more flexible, and more error-free systems (Yardımcı Coşkun, Baskak & Tanyaş, 2025). Digital technologies emerging with the Industry 4.0 revolution have created a fundamental transformation in warehouse management. Thanks to technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, robotic automation systems, big data analytics, and digital twin technologies, warehouses have become not only areas for storing products but also intelligent systems that generate data, analyze it, and provide decision support (Taşkın, Gezik, Yumuşak & Eren, 2022). On the other hand, environmental issues such as global climate change, the reduction of carbon emissions, and the sustainable use of natural resources force businesses to restructure themselves not only in economic terms but also in terms of environmental responsibilities. At this point, the concepts of sustainable logistics and sustainable warehouse management come to the forefront.

When these two transformation areas—digitalization and sustainability—come together, the concept of “smart and sustainable warehouse management” emerges. This approach is a holistic management model that aims both to increase operational efficiency and to minimize environmental impacts (Genç and Tunalı, 2022).

2. Literature Review

In this section, the concepts of digital transformation, the Industry 4.0 approach, and smart warehouse systems, which form the theoretical foundation of the research, will be addressed, and the Çumra Sugar Factory case will be presented in light of these concepts.

Digital Transformation and the Industry 4.0 Approach

Within the scope of digital transformation, one of the most frequently addressed topics is the concept of Industry 4.0, which aims to enable high technology to support production processes. Industry 4.0 is defined as a new industrial paradigm based on the integration of digital technologies in production and service systems. This paradigm aims to make production and logistics processes more intelligent, flexible, and efficient through the combined use of technologies such as cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, and big data analytics (Mercimek & Geçkil, 2021). It is a realistic approach to consider that smart factories, which can produce by self-optimizing and self-coordinating through the use of machines and cyber systems in manufacturing processes, will become part of our lives. With Industry 4.0, it is expected that production times and energy consumption will decrease, while production volume and quality will increase (Ertuğrul & Özdemir, 2020).

Industry 4.0 is described as working to produce faster and more reliable products in factories through systems that can manage and make decisions autonomously. Smart factories are autonomous devices that connect and transmit data between the physical and virtual worlds. Industry 4.0 transforms human labor into automation (Şener and Elevli, 2017).

Smart Warehouse Systems

The concept of a smart warehouse has emerged as a result of the integration of traditional warehouse management systems with digital technologies. These systems are based on real-time data flow, automated decision-making mechanisms, and process optimization. The

primary objective of smart warehouse systems is to increase service quality and overall efficiency in warehouses while also reducing costs and errors (Van Geest et al., 2022).

Smart warehouse systems are an important component of supply chain management in providing easy and efficient logistics operations for companies. Since logistics costs constitute a significant part of overall production, these operations determine a company's competitiveness. In order to control warehousing costs, many companies utilize emerging technologies, particularly in the fields of supply chain and logistics. According to popular and academic studies, warehouse management is one of the most important components of the supply chain. Since the warehouse is a place that ensures the flow of materials throughout the supply chain, attention is also given to the performance and design of warehouse operations, alongside other important functions that contribute to increased operating costs. Therefore, in today's businesses, the warehouse is a crucial part of the supply chain that needs to be further developed (Gu et al., 2007; Berg, 1996; Kamali, 2019; Frazelle, 2002). In warehouses, machine operators or human labor are used in processes such as placing materials on shelves, retrieving them from shelves and transporting them to shipping areas, and performing physical movements during address changes. However, in the current situation, problems such as material damage, incorrect shipments, expiration issues in warehouses, and time loss occur due to the human factor. As a result, warehouse management should be reconsidered through technology and supported with Industry 4.0 applications, and smart warehouse systems should be established.

The use of smart warehouse systems provides several benefits, such as accelerating loading and unloading operations, reducing workplace accidents, ensuring computer-aided inventory control, responding more quickly to customer demands, lowering storage process costs, strengthening communication between production, supply, and warehousing, reducing human errors, improving energy efficiency, and enabling remote control. According to Yılmaz (2023), smart warehouse systems improve logistics performance not only in terms of speed but also in terms of accuracy and cost-effectiveness. In addition, smart warehouse systems provide competitive advantage by offering more customer-oriented, effective, and efficient services. The main components of smart warehouse systems are as follows: ERP systems, smart robots, smart storage and retrieval systems, automated guided vehicles, and the Internet of Things (IoT). Through these technologies, in-warehouse processes are optimized without the need for manual intervention, error rates are minimized, and operational speed is significantly increased.

Case of Çumra Sugar Factory

Established in 2003 and fully financed through internal resources, Çumra Sugar Factory was completed in 2004 and has become one of the most advanced sugar factories in the world. Covering a circular area with a 20 km radius, this facility is the largest sugar factory in Türkiye. The smart warehouse at the Çumra Sugar Factory is 38 meters high, seismically resistant, and has been established as a fully automated system. This system controls the logistics operations of snack products. The warehouse uses the Mecalux computerized automation system, which is one of the most advanced technologies in the world, providing high efficiency in product storage and shipment. Thanks to this system, storage and logistics operations are managed without human intervention. Since the structure is 38 meters high and covers a large area, large items can be stored vertically, and it has a high storage capacity.

The warehouse is safe against earthquake risk thanks to its seismic-resistant structure. It is integrated into the snack production facilities of the Çumra Sugar Factory, and in this way, transportation costs for moving products to the warehouse have been minimized, while time losses and waste that may arise from handling and transportation have also been prevented.

3. Methods

This study, which is a qualitative research design, was conducted using the semi-structured interview technique, one of the qualitative data collection methods.

3.1. Study Setting and Population

The population of the study consisted of managers of large-scale manufacturing and logistics enterprises operating in Konya, Türkiye, that actively use smart warehouse systems. Permission to conduct the study was requested from five major logistics companies in Konya utilizing smart warehouse systems; however, only one company granted approval for participation. The participants of the study consisted of the smart warehouse application managers of Çumra Sugar Factory who agreed to participate in the study (N = 5).

Çumra Sugar Factory is a large-scale industrial enterprise representing different levels of digital maturity and various sectors. Operating under the Torku brand, the company markets its products to both national and international markets. Çumra Sugar Factory (Konya Şeker) is not limited to sugar production; through its integrated facilities, it also manufactures a wide range of food and snack products (such as biscuits, chocolate, wafers, etc.).

3.2. Data Collection and Analysis Method

The researchers developed a semi-structured interview form. The interview form included eight questions related to smart warehouse technologies, nine questions related to sustainability and energy efficiency, six questions related to operational efficiency, five questions related to traceability and food safety, and four questions related to corporate vision and future plans. The interviews were conducted in a quiet room at a time convenient for the participants. The interviews were audio-recorded with the participants' consent. The audio recordings were transcribed into written text by the researchers, and the interview transcripts were read repeatedly prior to analysis to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the data. The interview transcripts were transferred to a Word document and analyzed using the content analysis method with MAXQDA Version 10.

In the analysis of the data obtained in this study, qualitative content analysis was employed as one of the qualitative data analysis methods. Content analysis is a method that enables the systematic classification, categorization, and interpretation of information obtained from qualitative data sources such as interviews, observations, and documents (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). The primary objective of content analysis is to organize the collected data under specific themes and to generate meaningful findings related to the research problem. The main reason for selecting content analysis was its ability to facilitate an in-depth examination of the data obtained from participants' perspectives and to enable detailed evaluations concerning the research problem. Furthermore, it contributes to the systematic and meaningful presentation of the study results.

In the first stage of the analysis, meaningful statements were identified in line with the purpose of the study, and primary codes were generated from these statements. The coding process was carried out using an inductive approach, with the codes being derived directly from the participants' statements. In the second stage, codes with similar meanings were grouped together to form categories. Subsequently, the similarities and relationships among these categories were examined, leading to the development of higher-level abstractions in the form of themes. Throughout the analysis process, the constant comparative method was employed, whereby newly obtained data were continuously compared with the existing codes and categories, and the analytical framework was regularly reviewed and refined. The coding and

theme development process was subsequently re-evaluated by the researchers, and the final structure was established through consensus.

To enhance the trustworthiness of the findings, direct quotations from the participants' statements were included, and the thematic structure was supported by these quotations. As a result of the analysis, a comprehensive conceptual framework consisting of themes, categories, and primary codes was developed to explain the effects of smart warehouse technologies on sustainable warehouse management.

3.3. Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by the Social Sciences Ethics Committee of Necmettin Erbakan University (Decision No. 2025/720). Subsequently, research permission was obtained from Çumra Sugar Factory. The participants were informed about the purpose and procedures of the study, and their informed consent was obtained prior to participation.

4. Results

Five middle- and senior-level managers responsible for overseeing the smart warehouse systems of a large-scale sugar factory participated in the study. All participants held university degrees, and their years of professional experience ranged from 5 to 15 years.

Analysis of the participants' responses revealed two main themes. The first theme was "Technological and Operational Transformation through Smart Warehouse Systems," while the second theme was "Sustainability and Corporate Development in Smart Warehouse Management."

4.1. Technological and Operational Transformation through Smart Warehouse Systems

Within the main theme of "Technological and Operational Transformation through Smart Warehouse Systems," five subthemes emerged: Digital Transformation and Automation, Operational Efficiency and Process Optimization, System Reliability and Continuity, Food Safety and Traceability, and Future Orientation and Innovation (Table 1). Participants stated that digital transformation and automation in warehouse processes have significantly improved operational processes. Within the theme of "Digital Transformation and Automation," the categories of integrated digital warehouse infrastructure, smart identification and tracking technologies, automation-based warehouse control, and real-time digital management emerged as prominent. The use of Siemens S7-300, PLC, WMS, Gallile, and SCADA systems, the active utilization of RFID, barcode sensors, and handheld terminals, the management of warehouse operations through automation systems, and the real-time monitoring of processes were identified by the participants as important primary codes (Table 1).

Within the theme of "Operational Efficiency and Process Optimization," the categories of reducing manual dependency, error minimization, process acceleration, accurate inventory and shipment control, workforce optimization, and rapid logistics accessibility emerged. Limited weekly manual intervention, the reduction of shipment error rates to a minimum level, the provision of faster and more accurate shipment processes, the placement of inventory in correct locations, the ability to perform a greater number of error-free shipments with fewer personnel, and the provision of rapid and easy access to products were the primary codes that emerged under this theme (Table 1).

Under the theme of "System Reliability and Continuity," the categories of technical support integration, rapid fault intervention, and continuous operational monitoring were identified. The implementation of remote maintenance and software updates, the provision of technical

Table 1: Themes, Categories, Primary Codes, and Participant Quotations of the Main Theme of Technological and Operational Transformation through Smart Warehouse Systems

Main Theme 1: Technological and Operational Transformation through Smart Warehouse Systems			
Themes	Categories	Primary Codes	Participant Quotations
Digital Transformation and Automation	Integrated digital warehouse infrastructure	Use of Siemens S7-300, PLC, WMS, and Galileo systems	“We use Siemens S7-300 PLC programming, the Galileo SCADA system, and warehouse management software (WMS).” (Interview 2)
	Smart identification and tracking technologies	Use of RFID, handheld terminals, and barcode sensors	“We use RFID handheld terminals and barcode scanning sensors.” (Interview 2)
	Automated warehouse control	Management of warehouse operations using Siemens S7-300 and monitoring via SCADA systems	“Siemens S7-300 PLC systems are managed, and they are monitored via the Galileo SCADA system.” (Interview 2)
	Real-time digital management	Real-time monitoring and data management	“Yes, it is carried out in real time, instantaneously.” (Interview 5)
Operational Efficiency and Process Optimization	Reduction of manual dependency	Limited weekly manual intervention	“Manual intervention is carried out a few times per week.” (Interview 4)
	Error minimization	Reduction of shipment error rates to a minimum level	“Shipment error rates have been reduced to a minimum level.” (Interview 5)
	Process acceleration	Faster and more accurate shipment processes	“There has been faster and more accurate shipment.” (Interview 3)
	Accurate inventory and shipment control	Correct stock coding and location-based storage of inventory	“It has been ensured that products are accurately stored in their designated locations with correct stock codes, without errors.” (Interview 2)
	Labor force optimization	More accurate shipment operations with fewer personnel	“More shipments are carried out with fewer personnel, with no errors.” (Interview 2)
	Rapid logistics accessibility	Fast and error-free product shipment	“Products intended for dispatch can be accessed quickly, easily, and without errors.” (Interview 2)
System Reliability and Continuity	Technical support integration	Remote maintenance and software update	“Company representatives perform maintenance and updates via remote access.” (Interview 4)
	Rapid fault intervention	Technical response within four hours in case of malfunctions	“In case of errors or malfunctions, they intervene in the system and resolve it within a maximum of 4 hours.” (Interview 2)
	Continuous operational monitoring	Ongoing supervision of operational errors by technical teams	“There is a team that continuously monitors these errors and malfunctions.” (Interview 4)
Food Safety and Traceability	Digital traceability systems	Three-month retrospective traceability capability	“Data can be traced retrospectively for up to three months.” (Interview 5)
	Environmental monitoring for food safety	Automatic climate control and environmental tracking systems	“The automatic climate control system records and maintains this data.” (Interview 5)
	Safe food storage operations	Protection of products against external environmental factors	“Products are fully protected against external factors.” (Interview 4)
Future Orientation and Innovation	Long-term operational growth strategy	Plan for increasing warehouse capacity in the long term	“In the long term, capacity expansion is anticipated.” (Interview 4)

intervention within a short period in the event of system failures, and the continuous monitoring of operational errors by technical teams were evaluated as important primary codes supporting system reliability (Table 1).

Within the theme of “Food Safety and Traceability,” the categories of digital traceability systems, environmental monitoring for food safety, and safe food storage operations emerged. The retrospective traceability of products, the monitoring of environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity through automated systems, and the protection of products from external factors were among the primary codes identified as making significant contributions to food safety. Finally, within the theme of “Future Orientation,” the category of long-term operational growth strategy was identified; planning aimed at increasing warehouse capacity in the future was evaluated as an important primary code (Table 1).

4.2. Sustainability and Corporate Development in Smart Warehouse Management

Within the main theme of “Sustainability and Corporate Development in Smart Warehouse Management,” four themes emerged: Environmental Sustainability, Economic Sustainability and Resource Management, Corporate Vision and Strategic Competence, and Human Resources Challenges (Table 2). Participants stated that smart warehouse systems significantly affect not only operational processes but also economic sustainability, environmental practices, corporate capacity, and human resource management. Within the theme of “Environmental Sustainability,” the categories of smart environmental control, waste management systems, recovery-oriented waste management, and environmental performance limitations emerged. Participants identified the use of temperature-sensitive automatic heating and cooling systems, the separation of plastic and wooden pallet waste, and the delivery of waste products to authorized recycling companies as important primary codes. However, the absence of carbon footprint and energy consumption calculations was also expressed as a notable limitation in terms of environmental sustainability (Table 2).

Within the theme of “Economic Sustainability and Resource Management,” the categories of workforce efficiency, space optimization, and equipment efficiency were identified. Conducting more operations with fewer personnel, utilizing warehouse space more efficiently, and reducing equipment requirements through automation were among the important primary codes supporting economic sustainability. Participants particularly emphasized that achieving high pallet storage capacity within limited space provides a significant advantage (Table 2). Within the theme of “Corporate Vision and Strategic Competence,” the categories of organizational competence and strategic corporate vision emerged. Proceeding with the transition to the smart warehouse system without receiving external consultancy and managing the process in accordance with the knowledge, foresight, and vision of the institution’s own employees were evaluated as important primary codes. This finding indicates that the institution possesses the capacity to develop systems tailored to its own operational needs (Table 2). Finally, within the theme of “Human Resources Challenges,” the category of qualified workforce shortage was identified. Participants stated that although smart warehouse systems reduce workforce requirements, they experience difficulties in finding trained personnel with the technical knowledge necessary to operate these systems. Therefore, the shortage of qualified technical personnel emerged as a significant challenge for the sustainable management of digital warehouse systems (Table 2).

Table 2: Themes, Categories, Primary Codes, and Participant Quotations of the Main Theme of Sustainability and Corporate Development in Smart Warehouse Management

Main Theme 2: Sustainability and Corporate Development in Smart Warehouse Management			
Environmental Sustainability	Smart environmental control	Temperature-based automatic heating and cooling systems	“There is an automatic climate control system that provides heating in winter and cooling in summer.” (Interview 2)
	Waste management systems	Plastic and wooden pallet waste management	“We have waste plastic and wooden pallet management practices.” (Interview 5)
	Recycling-oriented waste management	Sale of waste materials to authorized recycling companies	“Waste materials are sold through tender to authorized companies.” (Interview 4)
	Environmental performance limitations	Lack of carbon footprint and energy consumption calculations	“No, such calculations are not performed.” (Interview 1)
Economic Sustainability and Resource Management	Labor efficiency	Reduction in labor requirements	“Timely shipments are carried out with fewer personnel.” (Interview 2)
	Space optimization	High pallet storage capacity in a limited warehouse area	“Accurate and fast shipments are ensured with a high pallet storage capacity in a limited space.” (Interview 2)
	Equipment efficiency	Reduction of equipment needs through automation	“Accurate and fast shipments are ensured with fewer personnel and less equipment.” (Interview 5)
Corporate Vision and Strategic Competence	Internal organizational capability	Establishment of the smart warehouse system without external consultancy	“No consultancy services were used.” (Interview 5)
	Strategic corporate vision	Managing the transition process through organizational foresight	“It was implemented through the foresight and vision of our internal units.” (Interview 5)
Human Resources Challenges	Skilled workforce issues	Difficulty in finding trained technical personnel	“It is difficult to find qualified personnel.” (Interview 5)

The study results indicate that smart warehouse systems provide significant operational and organizational advantages while also presenting certain implementation challenges. These findings are summarized in Figure 1.

Among the positive outcomes, participants particularly emphasized the reduction of operational errors, the acceleration of shipment processes, the decreased need for workforce, and the improvement of product traceability. Through the use of automation systems, barcode technologies, RFID applications, and real-time monitoring mechanisms, more accurate inventory management and faster shipment processes can be achieved with fewer personnel. Furthermore, digital traceability systems enable the retrospective tracking of products and warehouse processes, thereby enhancing product safety and operational reliability (Figure 1). However, participants also highlighted several important challenges associated with smart warehouse systems. In particular, the high cost of automation investments was identified as a significant barrier limiting the widespread adoption of technological advancements. In addition, difficulties in recruiting qualified technical personnel capable of managing advanced automation systems emerged as a major organizational challenge.

Figure 1. Positive Outcomes and Challenges of Smart Warehouse Systems

From a sustainability perspective, the limited use of renewable energy sources and the absence of carbon footprint measurement systems were identified as shortcomings in environmental sustainability practices (Figure 1). Overall, the findings indicate that smart warehouse systems significantly strengthen operational efficiency and economic sustainability; however, environmental sustainability and the development of a qualified workforce remain key areas requiring further improvement.

Based on these results, the Smart Warehouse Sustainability Model was developed to present a holistic framework explaining the multidimensional contributions of smart warehouse systems to sustainable warehouse management (Figure 2). The model is fundamentally based on technological infrastructure, and digital technologies such as WMS, SCADA, Siemens S7-300, RFID, and barcode systems enable the automation and real-time management of warehouse processes. This technological transformation supports operational optimization, contributing to the reduction of error rates, the increase of shipment speed, and the more efficient use of labor and equipment. In addition, through the dimensions of traceability and food safety, it becomes possible to track products on a batch and lot basis, to automatically monitor temperature and environmental conditions, and to maintain food safety standards. The model's economic sustainability dimension focuses on providing cost advantages through fewer personnel and more efficient space utilization, while the environmental sustainability dimension encompasses energy efficiency, waste management, and recycling practices. In addition, the model emphasizes the importance of corporate vision and organizational competence; it demonstrates that sustainable success is possible not only through technology investments but also through a strategic management approach, technical knowledge, and qualified human resources. Overall, the model reveals that smart warehouse systems constitute a strategic structure that provides operational efficiency, reliability, customer trust, and sustainable competitive advantage.

Figure 2. Smart Warehouse Sustainability Model

5. Discussions

The results of this study reveal the importance of Industry 4.0 technologies and smart warehouse systems in the logistics sector. However, a number of barriers have also been identified for the widespread adoption and effective use of these technologies. Obstacles such as personnel adaptation problems, high investment costs, and the technology adaptation process need to be overcome.

Logistics companies in Türkiye perceive innovative technology investments as high-cost (Genç & Tunalı, 2022). On the other hand, the limited availability of human resources capable of using advanced technology also leads enterprises to remain distant from high-technology investments.

The application of Industry 4.0 technologies in the logistics sector increases the measurability of logistics operations, enables production processes to spread over a wider area, facilitates collaboration with autonomous technologies, and allows distribution planning to be carried out in a clearer and more accurate manner (Tubis & Rohman, 2023). The logistics sector, in a highly competitive environment, must adapt to the innovations brought by technology. Technologies such as smart factories, robots, smart warehouses, autonomous vehicles, and blockchain will increase the traceability of supply chain processes. The logistics sector will change significantly with the increased use of these technologies. Therefore, human labor-based tasks in the logistics sector will gradually decrease and new fields will emerge (Ivanov & Dolgui, 2021).

One of the most important findings of this research, which examines the effects of smart warehouse applications on sustainability performance, is that performance measurements become significantly easier and can be conducted more frequently through smart warehouse applications. Participants stated that RFID systems, barcode technologies, WMS software, and automation-based warehouse management applications increase the traceability of inventories, accelerate shipment processes, and reduce error rates. These findings are consistent with the study by Genç & Tunalı (2022), which demonstrates improved logistics performance in terms of smart warehouse measurement speed, accuracy, and cost. Similarly, Tubis & Rohman (2023) found that AI-supported logistics analytics are enhanced. This study also showed that, in particular, real-time data management and automatic control systems play an important role in the effective and efficient management of warehouse operational processes.

The study results have shown that smart warehouse applications contribute to the optimization of the workforce. Participants stated that faster and smoother shipments can be carried out with fewer personnel. This result supports the evaluations of Ivanov & Dolgui (2021) that human labor-based tasks in the logistics sector will decrease, and automation systems will become widespread. However, there is a notable and significant difference. In the literature, the use of automation systems is generally expressed as a positive development in terms of reducing labor costs. In this study, however, this situation emerged as an important problem in the form of a lack of technical personnel. Human resources are very important in digital transformation. In particular, it is difficult to find trained personnel who can manage the system. This shows that technological efficiency requires the existence of both hardware and human capital investments.

The results obtained within the scope of the study reveal that smart warehouse systems provide significant contributions to businesses in terms of both improving operational processes and supporting sustainable corporate development. In line with participant opinions, it has been determined that RFID technologies, barcode systems, WMS (Warehouse Management System) software, and automation-based warehouse applications make stock processes more systematic, accelerate shipment processes, reduce error rates, and contribute to the more efficient use of labor. In addition, thanks to real-time data management, the ability to monitor warehouse

operations instantaneously enables processes to be carried out in a more controlled manner, thereby increasing operational efficiency. These results show that digitalization in logistics activities through Industry 4.0 provides significant advantages to businesses in terms of speed, efficiency, and process control. However, the research findings also show that smart warehouse systems are not limited to improving operational processes; they also contribute to sustainability performance through energy efficiency, waste management, recycling practices, and effective management of resource utilization. This situation shows parallelism with Alkış, Pirtini & Ertemel, (2022), who emphasizes the effect of sustainable practices in enterprises on environmental performance and competitive advantage. When evaluated in general, smart warehouse systems are considered a strategic management tool that increases operational efficiency, enables cost control, supports environmental sustainability, and enhances the corporate competitiveness of businesses.

Limitations of the Study

The most important limitation of the research is the small sample size. The reason for this is that, except for one of the enterprises from which permission was requested for the study, the others did not grant permission. Therefore, the study was conducted with a single enterprise. Since the individuals who could evaluate the smart warehouse applications in this enterprise and their effects on sustainability would be those at the management level, the number of participants also remained very limited. It would be useful for readers to take this limitation regarding the generalizability of the results into consideration.

6. Conclusions

Due to globalization, digitalization, and increasing competitive conditions, technological transformation in logistics and warehouse growth are necessary. Smart warehouse technologies developed with Industry 4.0 contribute to businesses gaining competitive advantage, using resources more efficiently, supporting sustainability goals, and ensuring effectiveness in cost management. In general, smart warehouse systems provide significant contributions to businesses in terms of operational efficiency, cost advantage, sustainability, traceability, and corporate competitiveness. However, it is certain that technological investments alone are not sufficient for the successful implementation of these technologies. In line with the results, it can be stated that human resources should be supported through training, organizational adaptation, and sustainability strategies.

When the results of the study are evaluated in general, it is seen that smart warehouse applications provide significant benefits in terms of speed, cost advantage, traceability, occupational safety, and sustainability. However, structural problems such as high investment costs, insufficient technical personnel, and performance measurement systems have also emerged. These results show that digital transformations should be addressed not only as technology investments but also through planning, human resources, and sustainability management.

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